

The Biggest Lie in the History of Science: We Have Been Made to Believe That Causes Create Effects!

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“As a result of the subliminal submessages and indoctrinations that materialist-naturalist-determinist epistemology, which dominates modern-secular science, imposes on our minds based on suggestion and repetition, our minds are formatted and reprogrammed. As a result of these infected messages and codes, we have been led to believe that causes cause or can produce results!”

Born in the 1600s and 1700s, in the Renaissance, Reform, and Enlightenment Triangle, and then hegemonizing the whole world, regardless of culture and geography, and not accepting any other epistemology, any other understanding of science, and even rejecting it; Modern–Secular Epistemology of Science; Since it is based on Atheist-Deist and Materialist, Naturalist-Determinist Philosophical Paradigms, while expressing raw observation, experiment, and measurement data and information, it axiomatically constructs sentences and expressions "without subject and agent." That is, “There is no God; if it exists, and even if it does, it does not interfere with the functioning of the universe." expressions are used in their sub-ground and context. In other words, he constructs sentences with the context of "the activities and results in the universe are not the actions and works of God." To the subconscious mind: This sub/subliminal message, suggestion and principle, code and programming, uses dirty viral expressions, and whispers softly to our subconscious in decibels that our consciousness cannot hear.

However, by using the “Reverse Engineering” Method; If we go from "results" to "reasons"; The one who does not have eyes knows "seeing" and the "act of seeing" and accordingly makes an "eye"; or the person who does not have "ears" knows "sound" and the "act of hearing" and accordingly makes an "ear"; Just as it is logically impossible and possible; as atom and molecule or system and organization; devoid of senses and feelings such as “eyes, ears, consciousness, mind”; that is, the "matter, force and energy" in the universe, which is "blind, deaf, unconscious and mindless" and most importantly, "inanimate"; such as eye and vision, ear and hearing, mind and reasoning, actions and works and results; Being or being a “cause”; Logically, it is impossible and impossible...

Just because they come before the effects or results and continuously, adjacent to the results and successive or consecutive, and because they apply forces such as "heat, light, pull, push,

pressure" to the results (objects and works), they are given the name "cause," and then it is not reasonable to believe that there is or could be a "cause" for the results. It is not logical to believe that causes cause effects.

Because, for example, "broom" alone is not a sufficient reason to sweep the floor. In other words, that broom lacks the will and power to act alone and sweep and clean the floor because it is solid and lifeless. Someone who has life, knowledge, will, and power must activate that broom with his power, aim, and will to sweep the floor. Conclusion: It is Allah Almighty who sweeps the floor, not the broom! Müsebbibü'l Esbab is Allah. So the reasons are that even being the cause and means of something is possible, thanks to Allah Almighty.

This, at most, is the role of causes in the universe. Even less than that. Because of the application of action-reaction laws and friction, movements of atoms, etc., that broom cannot even be a tool for sweeping. Because other laws and substances that go back to the Big Bang also need to be adjusted, Put simply, the broom's contribution to sweeping is minuscule. Conclusion: If it were not for the power of Allah Almighty, the broom could not sweep even a single grain of dust or even stand up! ...

This "concrete matter and energy" and "abstract laws and mechanisms" that we believe to cause the results are like a matchstick that hides from our eyes the "Great Puppeteer," like the mountain behind it, because it is right before our eyes. Since it stands in front of our eyes, it appears larger than the huge mountain behind it and prevents us from seeing that mountain; in other words, it acts as a curtain. However, we are not animals. Let's just be content with what we see; let's just believe what we see! Let's believe that just because a rabbit comes out of a hat, it gives birth to rabbits!...

We can reason the motion of a billiard ball with the impact of another billiard ball and convince the mind of this, but as a result of billions of billiard balls (i.e., atoms) and "gravity," electromagnetism, etc., winds hitting the billiard balls together, for example, a "person" or a "tree" appears, we cannot explain the epistemology of science with this analytical, particular reductionist, existence concept, and fiction. With this determinist-naturalist epistemology and ontology, we cannot reason.

These events occur constantly, like the dice constantly rolling six or six. In other words, we cannot explain the constant falling of the dice by "coincidence"! So we look for a trick on the dice. What happens, even if it happens occasionally, may be attributed to chance, but if the dice are constantly falling in the universe, insisting that it still happens due to natural causes and coincidences is nothing but stubbornness! In other words, these actions and activities in the universe are a result of the effects coming to the atoms from opposing directions. We cannot explain them by the collision and combination of these atoms. We cannot cause each other by pushing, pulling, colliding, sticking, or separating from various aspects. We cannot make the mind believe this.

We cannot explain these actions and events, which constantly occur in the universe, with the

"laws of nature, physics, and chemistry." Because, anyway, if there is a "law," it means that there is a force, an agent, and a programmer that causes matter, energy, and atoms to obey that law. Because: They are abstract and mental and have no concreteness or materiality; that is, the "Laws of Nature" that do not have a physical existence; they act on concrete matter, move that matter, energy, and atoms to certain places, stop them in certain three-dimensional coordinates, and build a "living person" or even an "inanimate table." The definition of "law" (Law of Nature) is impossible. Because, as we said, it is not possible for "abstract and mental" laws and laws to apply force to "concrete and external" matter, to direct matter and atoms to certain points, and to fix them at one point.

We write the law in our minds on paper; for example, because there is a law saying "You must stop at a red light," mindless and lifeless atoms do not obey that law in our minds on paper; they do not see any sanction, that is, an order or obligation, in this law.

Then: The one who writes that law also writes the application and sanctions of that law, applies them to the article, and makes it happen; "matter" complies with that law "without his knowledge"! Then: There is a "lawmaker," a "wise judge," who writes the fixed and universal laws in the universe, commands the atoms, moves the atoms with his power, and enforces the orders, rules, and laws...

Another example: a cause that aims, plans, and knows that the baby in the womb will suckle milk when it is born in the future, that is, our Lord; it prepares the baby for this world by having him practice sucking his thumb in his mother's womb before he is born... So: Only someone who plans and knows the future can write "present and past." Only someone who knows the entire scenario can design and write this fiction consistently and assign that role to the matter. It can direct humans and their cells in that direction; it can pull and/or push cells to predetermined coordinates.

In short, nothing happens in the universe because it is "possible." But we think it is "possible" because it has been happening constantly! This is a trick in our minds!

With today's mind, if we were born at the age of 15, "Who brought me here, where did I come from, and why did I come!? ... Oh! Very strange! A 'bird' emerges from the egg! ... From the colorless, tasteless, coarse soil that I stepped on with my foot and crumbled with my hand, we would look at everything and everywhere with amazement, saying, "Works of art come out in various colors and tastes!" But the custom and habit that begin at birth distort our perspective! Unfortunately, ignorance is the price we pay for not being able to establish the rapport we need with everything! ...

Yes, everything has a price: "Everything in the universe; it is possible for it to happen due to natural reasons, that is, due to the nature and properties of matter, on its own (that is, without an agent or master) and by chance; it is happening, so it is possible for it to happen"; a vicious circle (like a snake biting its tail, a vicious circle); that is, if we believe in the tautological, corrupt syllogism in which evidence and argument, cause and effect, are constantly replaced;

such as self-fulfilling belief (or claim, prophecy); everything seems that way to us. (Like someone who believes that someone is following me or people don't like me, he interprets every behavior he sees from people, that is, sees it that way.)

In short, “There is no God; He does not see; He does not do these things!” If we believe or act like that, our Lord treats us the same way! He acts like "it doesn't exist"! We can also view the hadith from this perspective: "I am as my servant thinks..."

From previous articles: “We cannot see the answer to the question we do not ask... There is no right answer to the wrong question. So, before finding the right answers, we must learn to ask the right questions. Whatever you look for, you'll find... Look for what you are looking for in the place where you lost it. The right question is half of the knowledge... Some of us definitely remember expressions such as... Here we are. If we approach events, events, facts with the right questions, only then can we see the answer there, in what is happening! Or, “How many letters's' are in this last paragraph?” without asking the question; we don't look for that answer; we don't see it; we don't notice it! ...

So, when looking at the universe, what is the right question? Which questions, when we examine the universe, reveal the answers and put an end to our search for meaning? ..

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As we said in our previous articles, it is independent and separate from “believing or not believing,” and these two options can be viewed impartially and from an equal distance. In other words, a neutral and objective "form of knowledge" or "form of expression" is not possible. Because in the universe, something we observe and examine, we can either look at it as if "there is a creator and a ruler" or as if "there is not." And according to this option we chose at the beginning, we express our observation information. Because, due to the logic of the language and the language of logic, there is no middle ground, external observation, or coordinate point between these two options! In other words, from an epistemological and ontological perspective, there is no third alternative, no third option that we can choose, go to, or look at!

Modern Science: Because he sees all "beliefs", right and wrong, as a "virus" that disrupts the objectivity and objectivity of 'knowledge', he has moved to the side of "disbelief"! However, “disbelief” is also the result of a “subjective” perception and attitude. So, like belief, disbelief is also a "subjective" attitude!

Transcending countries and cultures; in our age, it has become commonplace and mainstream; Modern-SSecular Science Philosophy and Episteme, due to this subjective and biased attitude; scientific observation: measurement information and data obtained from the

universe; The design takes an atheist's perspective into account. "Scientific information and data" collected from the universe constructs and expresses itself in an atheist-materialist-naturalist context.

Aside from the fact that this distinction between "religion class and science class" is not logically possible, Without real applicability and sustainable reality, our religion does not accept these false and virtual distinctions.

In other words, "Our Lord, the Prophet, the Book..." is not only the subject of "religion lessons," like "matter, energy, space, and time," but also our Lord's actions and works; it is not just the subject of courses such as "Physics, Chemistry, and Biology" of our religion; the holistic and holistic "Tawhid Paradigm" does not allow these false distinctions; since the third option we explained above is excluded, we can do this; He does not see it as sustainable, real, and logical.

The concepts of knowledge and science are not synonymous.

As a solution proposal to this wrong epistemology and philosophy of secular science and the science and textbooks written with this understanding, the first thing to do before setting off is to produce our concept schema and meaning maps and to reach consensus on them.

For example, we can start by making a distinction between "information" (data, information, and knowledge) and "science.". Observation, measurement, and interpretation of the universe and the "information" (data, information, and knowledge) within it, according to "secular and laic (more precisely, 'independent of religion'; more precisely, 'atheist') scientific criteria and methods resulting in disinformative and manipulative "filtered information"; in other words, we call the state of "knowledge" that has passed through the prism and interpretation/filter of "secular-secular science", "science".

"There is no God (atheism or denial); it is based on a "conception of the universe" that can be summarized as "even if it exists, it does not interfere with its functioning (deism or polytheism)"; we do not have to accept this concept of science (ontology and epistemology).

In scientific publications and textbooks: "Instead of divine, natural; formation rather than creation; instead of divine guidance and inspiration, natural guidance and instinct; instead of God's miracle, nature's miracle; instead of God's permission and will, it happened by chance and randomly..." such as containing this perception and submessage; the use of concepts and expressions "without agent and subject or with false agency"; we are against dictation as a requirement of scientific publishing and curriculum.

We do not accept this model of your universe that you have constructed according to your axiom, presupposition, or belief that "Matter and Energy + Long Time and Coincidence + Nature and Necessity + Law and Evolution = Everything is Possible."

Because of this "atheist-deist and materialist-naturalist" understanding that dominates the

current science and textbooks, every "reason and mechanism," every "description and explanation" about the functioning of the universe cuts and breaks the threads of relationship between "existence and our Lord" in our minds a little more every day. This atheist and naturalist dirty, viral science of yours, packaged as 'Scientific Knowledge', distorts our world of perception and meaning and our associations.

Because: the universe; thus, (supposedly) "independent and separate from our Lord and without needing Him"; Supposedly like an "automatic machine and computer"; committed "by itself"; injecting and indoctrinating perception and subliminal message; of these science and textbooks; Since kindergarten, it has been repeatedly suggested and repeated. It causes us to lose our Muslim thinking skills and reflexes.

As a result, all textbooks and curricula in schools, such as 'physics, chemistry, biology, geography, etc.' Unless this dirty and infected information is disinfected and cleaned, and unless these books are rewritten according to our own concepts, meanings, and civilization maps, Even if we give students 1000 hours of religion lessons and sira lessons a week at school, even if we memorize the entire Quran and hadiths, it does not bring about the expected change in mind and behavior in that student and person (like the fact that even if we put the best quality gasoline into a broken car, it does not help, or food does not benefit a sick person; it can even cause harm).

Because in Science class: "Rain; "It rains with this and that reason—mechanisms..." and in the next Religion lesson: "Rain; It rains because of Allah and as His mercy, blessing and blessing..." Most of us are deprived of the information and data that can bridge the disconnect and gap!

And because we are deprived:

"Since it is raining, this and that reason—it rains with mechanisms. In that case, where is Allah Almighty in this matter!? Since these material causes and systems shown by science can and do do this job, for me to believe in God, what is my rational or observational justification and evidence!? In this deterministic universe drawn from secular science, what does God do, or is there a need for God!? Those of us who lack the knowledge to answer questions and doubts such as: He can be an atheist or a deist; he begins to believe in a hypothetical "First Cause God"!

In short, it is as if it is independent and separate from "believing or not believing"; supposedly saying "secular-laic" education; In fact, with these science, textbooks, and curricula written through the eyes of an "atheist-naturalist" and with the concepts and expressions they can use, these schools that are foreign to our own sphere of meaning are, in our opinion, much more dangerous and harmful than 'missionary' schools!

These "atheist-deist and naturalist" beliefs and philosophies that are coded into our minds with the Hidden Persuasion Method and subliminal messages; injecting these misinformation viruses into our minds; these sciences and textbooks—it is much more dangerous and harmful

than books and publications that openly and obviously advertise and propagate blasphemy and polytheism!

Because by saying, "Believing is an objective and neutral science, independent and separate from not believing," "secular and secular education," and against this "dirty and viral information" that is inculcated into our minds with these perceptions and packages, since we do not have any defense or antivirus shields, we cannot notice these viruses and welcome them into our world of mind and meaning.

In this way, subliminal (or unconscious) messages—in other words, science and textbooks that secretly and insidiously encode "atheism—materialism and naturalism" into our minds and format and reprogram us—are much more effective, dangerous, and harmful than books and publications that publicly advertise and propagate blasphemy and polytheism!